

NCAS Capel Dewi
Atmospheric Observatory
<https://amof.ac.uk/observatory/>

Minutes of the 67th Capel Dewi Atmospheric Observatory Users' Meeting

which was held online on 16th July 2021.

(This document was finalised on 1st February 2022)

Attendees:

(BB)	Dr Barbara Brooks ^{4,6}	
(CJW)	Dr Chris Walden ^{4,5}	
(DAH)	Dr David Hooper ^{1,4,5}	Secretary
(EGN)	Dr Emily Norton ⁴	
(GV)	Prof Geraint Vaughan ^{4,7}	Chair
(GAP)	Dr Graham Parton ^{2,4,5}	
(HMAR)	Dr Hugo Ricketts ^{4,7}	
(LD)	Mr Les Dean ¹	

Affiliations:

¹Capel Dewi Atmospheric Observatory (CDAO)

²Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA)

⁴National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)

⁵STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)

⁶University of Leeds

⁷University of Manchester

Other abbreviations used in this document:

ALC	Automatic Lidars and state-of-the-art Ceilometers
DW	Dave Wareing
Mbps	Megabits per second
MST	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar)
NLC	Noctilucent Cloud
PAT	Portable Appliance Testing
RWP	Radar Wind Profiler
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UTC	Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

There were no comments on the minutes of the previous meeting.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 60.2.1 DAH to extend the availability of the v4 Cardinal files back to the earliest date for which v3 Cartesian files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that although there had been no action on this since the last meeting, data were now available from June 2006 to the present with only a few gaps.

ACTION ITEM 61.3.1 DAH to introduce a mechanism to allow users to access data files that have not yet passed quality control checks and been delivered to the CEDA archives.

ONGOING

DAH reported that James Groves had sent him details of how to make a directory on the JASMIN system web-accessible, although he had not yet implemented this. CJW assured him that it was quick and easy to do.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.1 DAH to make available the backlog of LD40 and WXT520 data in NCAS-approved files through CEDA.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had only been able to devote a small amount of time to this during the past 6 months.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.2 DAH to make available machine-readable files to show the number of MST radar transmitters in operation at any one time.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he would give an update on this in section 3a.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.3 DAH to come up with a plan for creating version 4 MST radar data for dates when no version 3 files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had not been able to devote any time to this during the past 6 months.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.1 DAH and GAP to implement a consistent archive structure for the different versions of MST Radar data products files.

COMPLETED

GAP reported that this action has now been completed. The datasets are available through the new path `/badc/ncas-cdao/` as well as through the older path `/badc/mst/`.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.2 DAH and CJW to arrange for installation of the new MST radar transmitters, which will require help from additional members of Chilbolton staff, for the latter part of 2019.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had contacted the Australian company that is due to carry out the work. They have indicated that they are in no position to send their staff to the UK under current Covid-19 restrictions. DAH added that he was waiting for a new mechanism to be created that will allow money to be transferred more easily from NCAS to STFC. This includes the funds held by NCAS for this action item.

ACTION ITEM 64.2.1 DAH and GAP to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar available through CEDA.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he and GAP had discussed where the data could be made available and in which format. The files produced by the Met Office are in a non-standard text-based format. GAP noted that these files would not formally constitute part of the MST Radar dataset. He therefore suggested that it was best to accept the data files as provided. GV agreed that this was the best solution.

ACTION ITEM 65.3.1 DAH to make enquires about the possibility of installing a fibre broadband connection to the CDAO.

ONGOING

DAH will report on his progress with this in section 3c.

GV wanted to know about the status of the surface wind data from Frongoch, which had not been covered by any action items. DAH said that he would give an update on this in section 4b.

3. Observatory Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

DAH reported that he and GAP had discussed how the MST Radar transmitter status monitoring data could best be made publicly available, i.e. addressing action item 62.2.2. He showed that the raw log files were in a simple comma-separated-variable format. Although DAH knows in principle what each of the 27 parameters represents, he has only ever focussed on the final 9 parameters. The most useful of these from the point of view of determining whether or not a transmitter is functioning is the final one, which gives the error code. Any value other than zero indicates that the transmitter was not in operation. DAH thought that the values of all 27 parameters should be included in a publicly-released file since he did not want to omit potentially useful information. He had initially considered using the BADC-CSV file format, but thought that netCDF would be easier to access for the types of users who are likely to want access to this information.

BB recommended [Grafana software](#) for visualising the transmitter status monitoring data. The software is already being used for other NCAS projects, e.g. for displaying [the latest surface met data from RHS Harlow Carr](#). BB recommended discussing the data requirements for action item 62.2.2 with the relevant users before deciding on how best to format the data.

3b) Electricity - DAH

DAH reported that he would arrange for a local electrical company to carry Portable Appliance Testing (PAT) at the CDAO as soon as possible. This job has been held up because of Covid-19 restrictions. Although LD had recently carried out PAT at the site, STFC do not regard this as being official since LD has not attended an STFC-approved training course.

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units switched to battery supply on 6 occasions during the past 6 months. Most of these were the result of short-lived (~1 s) issues with the mains supply. However, the last issue, which occurred at 03:56 UTC on 18th June 2021, lasted for 22 s.

BB reminded DAH that there was money from world class labs funding for new UPS units and IT equipment for the CDAO. She advised him to speak to James Groves.

3c) Telecommunications

DAH reported that he had finally succeeded in initiating the process to order a fibre optic connection to the CDAO, i.e. addressing action item 65.3.1. Until recently, Openreach had indicated that they were not able to offer this service in the Capel Dewi area. The installation will have to be paid for by the CDAO and is expected to cost around £32k. Line tests carried out by the internet service provider indicated that current download speeds are below 5 Megabits per second (Mbps) and upload speeds are below 1 Mbps.

At the previous meeting, DAH had reported that he had purchased two Draytek modem/routers in addition to the one already in operation on the main network. The intention had been to have one spare unit

for the main network and to use the other unit to make use of the broadband available on the “alarm line”. HMAR and Dave Wareing (DW) have subsequently made use of both of these units, although DAH is uncertain as to exactly how they are being used. GV clarified that there is an additional broadband-enabled telephone line to the lidar hut, which is paid for by Manchester. However, it did not appear to be working. BB recommended that the details of the different networks should be captured in a document.

EGN reported that the size of the data files produced by the Radar Wind Profiler (RWP) had increased much more than expected after the recent upgrade. In order to avoid using too much bandwidth, she is currently only transferring the smaller products files to Manchester.

3d) Miscellaneous

DAH reported that since Covid-19 restrictions had begun to be lifted, he had permitted visits to the CDAO to be resumed. Nevertheless, he is continuing to consult LD and DW before giving permission for such visits to go ahead. HMAR visited the site in late May 2021 and shorter visits have subsequently been made by representatives for NERC and Dyfed Alarms.

LD has drawn up plans for replacement “chicken shacks”, i.e. the structures that house the MST radar’s primary power splitters within the antenna array. LD had originally suggested making use of galvanised steel, since the plywood used for the existing structures had weathered badly. Moreover, there are a large number of companies available that could potentially manufacture the necessary panels. However, Richard Reeves of the Chilbolton Atmospheric Observatory has pointed out that the presence of metal sheets within the antenna array would have effects on the beam pattern (he also pointed out that the presence of rain water on the existing wooden structures would have a similar effect). He suggested that Glass-fibre Reinforced Polyester (GRP) might be a more-suitable construction material. DAH is trying to get help from both the STFC and NERC Estates teams to set up a contract for manufacture of the replacement units. GV emphasised that the poor state of the existing structures made this an urgent task.

ACTION ITEM 67.3.1 DAH to arrange for the replacement of the structures that house the MST Radar’s primary power splitters as soon as possible.

NEW

4. CDAO Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

DAH reported that single tips registered by the tipping bucket rain gauge on 4 occasions were likely to be the result of the accumulation of dew or the melting of frost/snow. These occurred at 08:40 UTC on 27th February 2021, 08:30 UTC on 1st March, at 08:10 UTC on 11th April, and at 08:30 UTC on 17th April. DAH has allowed these occurrences to remain in the publicly-available data files since the latter only have the capacity to mark data as missing, not as suspect.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

DAH reported that there is an ongoing problem with the 1 s interval wind directions being recorded by the logger. He has been prevented from investigating the cause of this by Covid-19 travel restrictions. HMAR reported that it had been easy to find accommodation in Aberystwyth during May 2021.

ACTION ITEM 67.4.1 DAH to visit Frongoch as soon as possible in order to resolve the problem of invalid direction values.

NEW

The 60 s interval NASA Ames data files record the wind vector as eastward and northward components. Since both are affected by the direction issue, there is no way of indicating that only the wind speeds are reliable. A new file type will be required in order to record the wind vector in terms of the speed and direction, each of which will have its own reliability flag. DAH indicated that this would be a good opportunity to change to netCDF files that are compliant with the NCAS-GENERAL data standard. GAP confirmed that CEDA provides tools for allowing people to output the contents of netCDF files in a text-based format. These are easier to handle for people who rely on software such as Excel for accessing data (it is known that a number of users of Frongoch data have fallen into this category).

DAH pointed out that users will generally need to apply further time-averaging to the 60 s interval data products in order to determine the sustained winds (DAH uses 15 minute averaging for the publicly-available plots). He asked whether such data products should also be included in the 60 s interval files. GV thought that it should be left to users to calculate such data products if they are required.

BB pointed out that standardised automatic weather stations will be purchased for each of the NCAS Atmospheric Observatories using world class labs funding. In addition to sensors for measuring pressure, temperature and humidity, there will be a Gill sonic anemometer, which takes measurements at 1 s intervals. BB's first thought was that the new equipment should be installed at Frongoch.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

DAH reported that he had had no time to deal with the data from this instrument since the last meeting. It was noted that the data from this instrument would be an ideal candidate for near-real-time plots.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

DAH reported that there had been a sudden change in the time stamp produced by the instrument's internal clock during the morning of 9th July 2021. This appears to have been caused by an interruption to the power supply. The internal clock is prone to drifting and so DAH has to hard code a time offset in his routine for creating [plots of the latest 24 hours' worth of data](#). He had to update the value of the offset in response to this issue.

In response to GV's enquiry, DAH explained that the drifting clock was the main issue to be resolved before he can make data from this instrument publicly available. Since the raw data are expected to be collected at 1 minute intervals, it is easy to infer the measurement times (to within a minute) if 1440 measurements are available for the day. The same is true if there are fewer than 1440 measurements, but the difference between the recorded times of the first and last measurements differ by 23 hours and 59 minutes. However, it is not immediately obvious how to interpret the recorded times under other conditions, e.g. if there has been a break in data acquisition that wraps around midnight. GV recommended that DAH should focus on those days for which the times can be reliably inferred, since this would allow him to release data for the vast majority of days.

4e) Lufft Ceilometer

HMAR reported that this instrument is working well. When he was on site in May 2021, he was able to establish that the alignment is still good. The transmitted power has dropped slightly, as would be expected. The laser unit is supposed to be replaced every 3 years and has already been in operation for 18 months. The data contributing to [E-PROFILE's Automatic Lidars and state-of-the-art Ceilometers \(ALC\) network](#) represent 15 minute averages. However, it is planned to make the 15 s interval profiles available through CEDA. HMAR is almost ready to release daily netCDF files that are compliant with the NCAS-GENERAL standard. GAP noted that [data from the entire E-PROFILE ALC network would be made available through CEDA](#).

BB asked whether plots of near-real-time data from this instrument could be made available. Such plots should be NCAS-branded and make use of a colour-blind-friendly colour map.

In response to BB's question about replacement laser units, HMAR reported that they cost around £2k. BB pointed out that there would be no import duty for an item delivered from Germany but VAT would apply.

4f) Sky Cameras

DAH reported that he had published a new time-lapse video, showing crepuscular rays, based on photos taken by the original sky camera. It is available from <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4782318>. The primary purpose of releasing this video was to test the potential of the [Zenodo open-access repository](#) as an alternative to the [CEDA document repository](#). GAP confirmed that the NERC Data Operations Group had approved Zenodo as an appropriate document repository.

4g) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

DAH reported that tropospheric cloud cover had been a limiting factor for the observations made by this camera during the 2021 summer season. The first unambiguous observation of NLCs was not made until the evening of 23rd June 2021. [The first MST-radar m-mode echoes of the season](#) were observed on 21st May 2021. [The first major m-mode echoes of the season](#) were seen on 2nd June 2021. DAH drew attention to the fact that the [standard plots of m-mode data](#) used to show data only for the Vertical beam observations, even when other beam pointing directions were available: the NE6.0 and SE6.0 beams are also typically used for m-mode observations during June and July. The standard plots now show data for all beam pointing directions available. DAH showed that [the m-mode plot for 4th June 2021](#) suggested that interference experienced by the [corresponding st-mode observations](#) 09:50 - 12:30 UTC was from the SE6.0 beam.

4h) MST Radar

DAH reported that the st-mode Cartesian files contained wind speeds that were inconsistent with those at adjacent times and/or altitudes on a number of occasions. On 2 occasions, these were confined to narrow time/altitude regions: 07:00 - 07:40 UTC on 18th March 2021 at around 17 km, and 06:10 - 06:50 UTC on 19th March 2021 at around 10.5 km. On another 6 occasions, these were over wider time/altitude regions and were the result of interference. The problem occurring 09:50 - 12:30 on 4th June 2021 was covered in the previous section.

There is a known software problem that mis-interprets the time stamps of data collected between 01:00 and 03:00 UTC on the morning when civil time changes from Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) to British Summer Time (BST). DAH had made changes to the code, which he thought would correct this issue. However, the new code simply created a different problem. DAH noticed this during the morning of Sunday 28th March 2021, when the civil time change occurred, and reversed the code change. The data products for apparent times between 01:00 and 06:45 UTC are affected by this issue and so should be ignored.

The publicly-available data files affected by the above issues have been released to CEDA labelled as containing suspect data.

A raised noise floor leads to reduced useful altitude coverage, but does not cause contamination of the data products. This was seen on 8 occasions, being most prevalent between 31st March and 2nd April 2021.

5. Guest Instrument Report

EGN reported that the upgrade of the Radar Wind Profiler (RWP) had been carried out in November 2021. Initially the beam did not appear to be steering and the observations all appeared to be made in the vertical direction. This turned out to be the result of a problem with a power supply rather than with the beam steering switch. The automatic Doppler scaling function had not been working during January

2021. This turned out to be the result of a Windows read/write permission setting, which affected communications between the PCA and PCT computers. There are still some minor issues, such as the PCA computer not starting cleanly.

EGN's ability to transfer data had been interrupted by changes to the firewall at Manchester. HMAR had created a work-around by setting up a local hub. In response to GAP's question, EGN clarified that data were only being sent directly to Manchester and not to JASMIN. The limited CDAO internet bandwidth was one of the reasons that she had taken this approach.

EGN has analysed the data from the post-upgrade period. The altitude coverage was good during Storm Christoph on 18th January 2021. This has allowed a comparison to be made with winds from the MST Radar, which shows good agreement. Mountain waves were seen on 9th May 2021. Unusual vertical velocity patterns were seen on 6th May 2021 (the MST Radar saw deep convection just before 12:00 UTC).

EGN has some outstanding actions. She needs to make plots of near real time data available. She will also need to make the data available in netCDF files that are compliant with the NCAS-GENERAL standard. The upgraded RWP now produces netCDF data files as standard. Nevertheless, EGN is still relying on the legacy binary data file format.

GV reported that the Raman lidar has not been working for some time. DW has been trying to resolve a number of issues. The Elight lidar is also out of action. DW and LD are currently trying to get it back in operation.

HMAR reported that he has been getting really good data from the sun photometer. The instrument was brought back to Manchester in May 2021 so that it could be used for an air quality observation campaign. HMAR hopes that it will return to Capel Dewi afterwards.

BB asked about the status of the lidar that is capable of measuring temperature profiles. HMAR reported that it was under development in the lab at Manchester. GV clarified that it was a proof of concept instrument. Although it is capable of being operated, the optics need a complete redesign.

6. Any Other Business

It was agreed that BB would take over as chair for these meetings after GV retires in September 2021. BB pointed out that most of the recent attendees have been members of NCAS staff and encouraged DAH to attract people from the wider community. GV pointed out that this would be easier to do if the science/technical presentations were re-instated (these have not been included since the meetings went online in 2020). He thought that the topics covered by the earlier sections of the meeting would be of limited interest to the wider community. DAH pointed out that it was likely that at least one of the twice-yearly meetings would remain online-only, in recognition of NCAS's environmental sustainability commitments. GV pointed out that the installation of the solid-state MST radar transmitters should lead to a reduction in electricity usage. He advised DAH to capture the details that would be needed to quantify this.

GV reported that he has continued to have discussions with Aberystwyth University about their proposed spectrum centre. The University is looking to have activities spread across a number of sites and is considering how the CDAO might be of use.

EGN reported that the RWP at the Chilbolton Atmospheric Observatory, which was gifted to NCAS by the Met Office, is in working order. She has been able to download the data that were collected prior to the instrument being gifted to NCAS. However, she is not sure if these data can be made publicly available. GAP thought that he would probably be able to apply the licence already used for Met Office data made available through CEDA.

The provisional date for the next meeting was set for late January or early February 2022.